

A Study of the B.Ed. Admission Process in Manipur: Challenges and OpportunitiesWormichon Raikhan¹ & Thanmichon Muinao²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18141397>**Review:26/12/2025****Acceptance:27/12/2025****Publication:03/01/2026**

Abstract: The admission process in teacher education institutions plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality and equity in teacher education institutions. Good quality admission process ensures transparency, fairness and equity in shaping and preparing prospective future teachers. This study focuses on the challenges faced by the students during admission to B.Ed. colleges and explores the opportunities that can enhance better results in paving the gateway to promising future for teacher educators. The present study adopted a descriptive survey method under quantitative research approach. 650 B.Ed. students from six different B.Ed. colleges of different districts in Manipur constituted the population of the study. Out of the 650 students, a sample of 120 B.Ed. students, 20 students each from the six B.Ed. colleges was selected through random sampling technique for the present study. A self-made questionnaire was used to collect the data from the students in order to assess the problems faced by the students during admission process in various aspects such as admission notification, allotment of seats, reservation policy, structure of fees and institutional support.

“The percentage, mean, t-test and standard deviation were used to analyse the information in order to determine the number of problems encountered by the aspirants in general when they were joining the B.Ed. Colleges, and the difference in the problems encountered by the aspirants depending on the gender and the streams”. The research revealed that the overall process of admission in The B.Ed. colleges in Manipur was good and effective. The research also indicated that admission process is neutral and like among streams because no significant degree of difference in problems encountered, according to the gender and across streams. The research findings reflect that the low scale difficulties and gaps in admission process at B.Ed. colleges should be tracked with the view of improving efficiency and inclusiveness of admission process further.

Keywords: Admission Process, B.Ed. Teacher Education, Challenges, Opportunities

Introduction: The field of Teacher Education forms the basis of sound and efficient education system in which the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) is significant in the preparation of well qualified teachers in the secondary level. The teaching profession holds the forefront in the growth of any teaching system since teachers assist in the formation of intellectual, societal and moral basis of the upcoming generations. Thus, admission to Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) is not a simple administrative procedure but significant steps to motivation and readiness of future teachers. This is done by the admission procedures and norms which map out the admission of the aspiring teachers and contours the systemic strengths and challenges of the aspirants. A transparent and efficient process also guarantees equal opportunity to deserving candidates and this increases the quality and standards of teacher education.

Although it has a formal structure, students usually experience challenges, including the inability to understand their procedures properly, delays in counseling, inconsistencies among institutions and poor advice to first-time

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applicants. Such challenges may affect the experiences of students, their teacher education, and their general satisfaction with the students. Also, the process provides a room of improvement in the area of transparency, following due procedures, availing online opportunities in terms of admissions, and providing assistance and improved information to potential applicants. In India, B.Ed. is considered as the required educational qualification for preparing trained teachers for educating secondary and higher secondary levels. The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has regulated norms and standards for B.Ed. colleges such as admission policy, reservation, eligibility criteria, intake capacity of students and selection procedures to maintain uniformity and uphold academic standards across different institutions.

However, implementation of these guidelines often varies due to various reasons like infrastructural, contextual and administrative differences. At present, there is a huge transition from offline mode to digitalization of admission process in higher education. Digital platforms indeed enhance ease of access and speed up the process to a large extent. However, in a state like Manipur, where there are many rural and tribal areas which have limited access to internet connections and technological resources challenge arises among the aspiring candidates.

Besides this, Manipur has a special socio-cultural and educational practice. The state has achieved a lot in the expansion of the educational access like teacher education but this has not been achieved yet because of the geographical location disparities, lack of facilities, digital divide, etc. The admission process of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur, in that regard, must be analyzed to the extent to which the policies are implemented into the reality. Once there should be a level and transparent admission process where all the aspirants should have the opportunity of being considered regardless of the caste, gender, academic stream, or rather socio-economic background. It should be friendly to students and have an easy access mode, be transparent, be cost effective and foster trust among the stakeholders. A biased admission process scares away the interested candidates and creates the impression of bias and lowers the standards of education. Thus, the discussion of the issues that the aspirants experience becomes a significant factor in offering an understanding of the good and bad practices within the current system. This paper analyses the B.Ed. admission procedure in Manipur that also addresses the issues students experience with as well as the opportunities it has to enhance efficiency and transparency. Through the analysis of the process currently existing, the study would provide some insight into the issue and make sure that the process of admission is a reliable and efficient gateway to quality teacher preparation.

The purpose of B.Ed. admission process is critical in determining the quality of teacher education by admitting worthy and competent candidates. Although it is significant, very few in-depth studies have been performed on the B.Ed. admission in Manipur. Also, the scope of study on the challenges and possible improvements are few and comprehensive. By exploring them, the current study will address the gap and offer the understanding of how the admission process could be improved and become more equitable.

This study can have beneficial implications on stakeholders (students, educational institutions, and policymakers). It will be possible to provide students with superior guidance and assistance in the admission process, to improve the procedures in colleges, and to increase the quality of teacher education by policymakers. Thus, the research is warranted because it will fill a big gap in the field of teacher education, it will add academic

knowledge and practical solutions towards fine tuning of the B.Ed. admission process within the state of Manipur.

Regulatory Framework:

The B.Ed. colleges in Manipur follow the guidelines prescribed by the NCTE Regulations (2014) which describe the norms related to eligibility criteria, reservation policies, selection procedures and intake capacity. "According to the guidelines given in NCTE (2014), the selection in B.Ed. colleges must be based on merits determined either by qualifying examination marks or entrance exams conducted by the affiliating universities or competent authorities. Candidates with at least 50% marks either in the Bachelor's Degree/Master's Degree in Sciences/Social Sciences/ Humanity, Bachelor's in Engineering or Technology with specialization in Science and Mathematics with 55% marks or any other qualification thereto, are eligible for admission to the programme. The reservation policies in B.Ed. colleges of Manipur are implemented as per the rules of Government of India and Government of Manipur, with seats reserved for Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes (ST), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and other eligible categories".

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were:

1. "To find out the overall level of problems faced by candidates during the admission process of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur"
2. "To make a comparative analysis of the extent of issues experienced by male and female applicants in the process of admitting B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur".
3. "To compare the degree of the issues encountered by science and arts applicants during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur"

Hypotheses of the Study:

The hypotheses of the study were:

1. "The overall level of problems encountered by the candidates in the admission process of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur is not significant".
2. "The level of problems encountered by male and female candidates during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur does not have much difference".
3. "The level of problems confronting science and arts candidates in the process of admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur does not have much difference".

Review of Related Literature

The B.Ed. college admission procedure has attracted the attention of scholars since it plays a major role towards the quality and equity of teacher preparation programme.

1. Admission Policies and Quality Assurance: Sound admission systems based on a practical administrative system are necessary in maintaining equity and academic excellence in teacher education institutions (Sharma and Singh, 2019). The analysis has pointed out that ambivalent selection eligibility requirements

and practices create confusion, and hence, potential candidates are discouraged to apply. These fears cause more systemic problems, though they can also be relevant in the case of Manipur.

2. **Role of Regulatory Bodies (NCTE):** In India, “the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE)” controls the process of admission in the B.Ed. colleges. C.T.E.(2014) reports that the quality of teachers has been enhanced through the introduction of well-regulated eligibility criteria and entrance tests. Nonetheless, the literature has revealed policy-institutional practice gaps especially in distant areas such as Manipur (Singh, 2020).
3. **Entrance Examinations and Merit-Based Selection:** Kumar and Bhatia (2018) suggested that entrance exams improve fairness and subjectivity in the admission process. The study merit-based selection gives an opportunity to competent candidates, but it becomes a challenge for those in rural and tribal students who have limited access to coaching and digital resources.
4. **Socio-Economic Barriers in Teacher Education Admissions:** Socio-economic factors greatly influence the access to admission in teacher education programs. Sharma and Singh (2019) found that students of economically weaker section face hardships during admission process due to high cost of fees, lack of awareness and limited institutional support.
5. **Online Accessibility:** Digital admission systems increase the efficiency of admission process and avoid delays. However, in regions like Manipur, internet accessibility is poor in many areas which result in unequal access to many students from remote rural or hilly areas (Singh and Devi, 2021). Many rural and tribal students face problems in online admission process due to poor internet connectivity and digital illiteracy.
6. **Gender and Equity:** Singh and Kumar (2020) studied the perception of candidates regarding admission process in teacher education institutions and found that the candidates are moderately satisfied with the process. “The study found no significant differences in the level of problems faced by male and female candidates indicating the admission practice in Manipur is gender-neutral and equitable”.
7. **National Education Policy (NEP 2020)** focuses on improving teacher education programs targeting better governance, digitization of administrative process and capacity building. Though not specifically confined to admission process, it covers educational which can enhance admission process overtime. However due to lack of digital literacy and infrastructural disparities, consistent monitoring, institutional support and infrastructural improvement is required.

Methodology:

- i. **Research Approach:** The researcher adopts a descriptive survey method under the quantitative research method in the present study. The descriptive method is suitable for the study as it examines the existing “admission process of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur” and identifies the challenges and opportunities associated with the process.
- ii. **Research Design:** “The research design is descriptive and analytical in nature as it examines the prevailing admission process of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur. It analyses the challenges and problems faced by the students during the admission process and explores the opportunities to improve transparency and efficiency of admission process”.
- iii. **Population of the Study:** “The population of the study included 650 student teachers of 6 B.Ed. colleges from 6 different districts in Manipur, namely Imphal West, Imphal East, Bishnupur, Churachandpur,

Senapati and Thoubal”.

Table showing the population of the study

S.N	Name of institute	Capacity	District
1	“D.M.College of Teacher Education”	150	Imphal West
2	“R.K. Sanatombi Devi College of Education”	100	Imphal East
3	Ruda Academy	100	Thoubal
4	“The Thokchom Ibotombi Institute of Teacher Education and Training”	100	Bishnupur
5	Bethany Christian Institute	100	Churachandpur
6	Mount Everest College of Teacher Education	100	Senapati

Source: NCTE website:

Sample and Sampling Technique:

- a. The researcher selected 20 student teachers from each of the six B.Ed. colleges belonging to six different districts of Manipur through a random sampling method for the present study.
- b. **Tool used:** The researcher used a self-made questionnaire to collect information from the B.Ed. students of the six colleges. The questionnaires were administered to the students with the prior permission of the head of the institutions. The tool consisted of 20 items with closed ended questions.
- c. **Statistical Technique:** The analysis of data has been done in conformity with the objectives and hypotheses formulated for the present study. The collected data were analyzed by using statistical techniques like percentage, t-test, standard deviation and graphs.

Analysis and interpretation

Objective 1: “To find out the overall level of problems faced by candidates during the admission process in B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

Graph 1 “showing overall level of problems faced by candidates during the admission process in B.Ed. colleges in Manipur.

The figure shows that the overall correct response was 86.34%, whereas the incorrect response was 13.66%. The

study found that the most of the candidates were satisfied with the advertisements, timely notification, and provision of equal allotment of seats in respect of gender, caste, stream and affordable fees. Hence, the first hypothesis was rejected as there was a high level of satisfaction in regards to admission process.

Objective 2: “To make a comparative analysis of the extent of issues experienced by male and female applicants in the process of admitting B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

Table 1. “Showing a comparative analysis of the extent of issues experienced by male and female applicants in the process of admitting B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”

Sl.No.	N	sex	mean	SD	SED	t-test	df
1	60	Male	17.33	03.63	03.01	00.21	119
2	60	Female	17.40	02.56			

The mean scores of the level of problems faced by males were 17.33, while the mean score of the level of problem faced by females were 17.40. The ratio of the two mean scores had a standard error of 03.01 with a t-ratio of 00.21, which is less than the level of significance (0.05). 86.65% of the male candidates faced problems whereas 87.00% faced problems during the admission process. Therefore, the second hypothesis of the study “There is no significant difference between the level of problems faced by male and female candidates during admission process in B.Ed. colleges” was accepted.

“There is no significant difference between the level of problems faced by male and female candidates during admission process in B.Ed. colleges” was accepted.”

Objective 3: “To compare the degree of the issues encountered by science and arts applicants during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

Table 2. “Showing the degree of the issues encountered by science and arts applicants during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

Sl.No.	N	sex	mean	SD	SED	t-test	df
1	60	Arts	17.55	2.05	03.07	1.15	119
2	60	Science	17.18	4.08			

“It can be observed from the above table that the level of problems faced by science and arts candidates were found to have a mean score of 17.55 and 17.18 with standard deviation of 2.05 and 4.08 respectively”. “The ratio of mean scores had a standard error of 0.03 with a t-ratio of 1.15, which is less than the level of significance. The level of problem faced by Arts trainees came out to be 17.55 (86.65%), whereas the level of problem faced by the science trainees was 17.18 (85.90%). Therefore, the third null hypothesis was accepted”

Findings

Objective-1: “To find out the overall level of problems faced by the candidates during the admission process in B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

From the study, we can understand that the admission process of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur is highly satisfactory in aspects of timely notification, affordable fee structures, easily accessible admission advertisements, fair allotment of seats to deserving candidates with respect to gender, caste and streams.

This result suggests that the admission process of B.Ed. colleges is highly efficient and transparent aligning the

norms regulated by the concerning bodies such as the NCTE. The first hypothesis was rejected as the students did not face high level of difficulty while seeking admission. The high level satisfaction reflects the administrative efficiency of B.Ed. colleges and supports the earlier studies which emphasized that clear information and merit based selection affects the satisfaction of students.

Objective 2: “To make a comparative analysis of the extent of issues experienced by male and female applicants in the process of admitting B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”.

From the analysis, the mean scores of male (17.33) and female (17.40) candidates were almost identical. This finding implies that the admission process is gender-neutral giving equal access to information, seat allotment and counselling across gender. Such results ensure that principle of equity and inclusivity in teacher education is emphasized and removes gender barriers in admission process.

Objective 3: “To compare the degree of the issues encountered by science and arts applicants during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur”

The findings indicate that arts students have slightly higher mean score (17.55) than the science students (17.18) but it was not statistically significant. So, the third null hypothesis was accepted. This result suggests that admission process does not favour or disadvantage candidates based on their streams indicating fairness and uniformity in the admission process.

Discussions: “The present study aims to examine the challenges and opportunities faced by the students during admission process of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur. The discussions are relative to the objectives formulated for the study and interpreted in the context of admission process in teacher education”.

1. The first objective determines the overall level of problems faced by the candidates during the admission process in B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur. The findings revealed that most candidates are satisfied with the admission process which suggests that the existing system is transparent, efficient and systematic. The students are highly satisfied with key aspects like timely notification, seat allotment, selection process and low fee structure. The study found that institutional mechanism and regulatory guidelines are well-implemented. The rejection of the first hypothesis indicates that the students do not experience high level of difficulty during the admission reflecting the growing emphasis on transparency and accountability of higher education.
2. “The second objective focuses on comparative analysis of the extent of issues experienced by male and female applicants in the process of admitting B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur. The findings revealed that the admission process is gender-neutral as there is no significant difference in the level of problem faced by male and female candidates during the admission process”. This indicates that gender does not act as a barrier in access to B.Ed. admission which is a positive indicator of inclusivity in the admission system. Equal treatment of male and female candidates boosts confidence in the procedure and ensures wider participation of students in teacher education programmes.
3. “The third objective focus on comparing the degree of the issues encountered by science and arts applicants during admission of B.Ed. Colleges in Manipur. The analytical findings indicate that there is no significant difference between the problems faced by science and arts students”. This result indicates that the system does not favor or discourage any particular stream which increases the credibility and uphold equity in the selection process.

Although the overall admission was found satisfactory, there were minor challenges faced by some candidates

which need to be addressed for ensuring quality in the admission process of teacher education institute. The discussion emphasized that improving infrastructure, administrative coordination and continuous monitoring can strengthen the admission process.

Conclusion

1. The study indicates that the admission process of B.Ed. colleges is satisfactory, fair and efficient adhering to the norms of NCTE Regulations (2014).
2. “The study revealed that the admission process is not gender bias as students of both gender faced no significant difference in the level of problems faced during the admission process”.
3. “The study also found that there is equity and uniformity across academic streams as there is no significant difference in the level of problems faced by science and arts students during admission process”.
4. The study concludes that while the admission process in B.Ed. colleges of Manipur is largely effective, continuous monitoring, standardization of procedures and enhanced digital support are necessary to address minor challenges and further improve efficiency and transparency. The study has important implications for policymakers, administrators, and teacher education institutions in strengthening admission practices and ensuring equitable access to teacher education.

Suggestions:

1. **Standardization of Admission Procedures:** All the teacher education institutes should follow a well-structured and standardized procedure to enhance the quality in preparing future teacher educators. The affiliating university must give clear-cut guidelines to avoid inconsistency and promote fairness and transparency in the admission process.
2. **Strengthening Online Admission Systems:** Digitization of administrative procedures widens ease of accessibility among students and ensures student-friendliness. Since many rural areas lack good connectivity and infrastructural problems, technical support and infrastructural improvement becomes a striking issue to be addressed.
3. **Timely and Clear Communication:** Admission-related information such as eligibility criteria, reservation policy, intake capacity and counseling schedule must be circulated timely and accessible manner through college websites, official whatsapp group, facebook or any other formal platforms.
4. **Establishment of Help Desks and Counseling Support:** The B.Ed. colleges must set up help desks to clear the confusion and misunderstandings of first – time applicants. Counseling cells must be introduced in the college to help the candidates address the queries throughout the admission process.
5. **Transparent Merit and Seat Allotment System:** The selection should be based on merits as envisioned in the guidelines of NCTE. Allotment of seats to students should follow the reservations & norms of the affiliating universities. Therefore, the concerned authority or affiliating universities must give clear guidance to the teacher education colleges.
6. **Training of Administrative Staff:** Trainings should be given to the administrative staff time to time so that they are tech-savvy and avoid procedural delays and improve efficiency.

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